

THE SUBDIVISION OF SARMATIAN DEPOSITS OF EASTERN GEORGIA BASED ON FORAMINIFERA

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The biostratigraphic correlation of Late Miocene deposits from different sectors of the Paratethys is very complex because of different biodynamic conditions established in the western, middle and eastern Paratethys beginning from the end of the Middle Miocene. In recent years great attention was paid to the biostratigraphic correlation of Late Miocene deposits from different sectors of the Paratethys (Maissuradze, 1980; Papp et al., 1974; Venglini, 1975; Cicha et al., 1998).

In Eastern Georgia, Sarmatian deposits have a wide distribution and are characterised by different fossil groups. Mollusks are currently considerably well known, however, some levels do not contain this group and correlation of the outcrops may prove difficult. Micropalaeontological investigations of foraminifera contained in Sarmatian sediments of Eastern Georgia are in the initial phase. This research provides new data on the vertical distribution of foraminifera from Sarmatian deposits of Eastern Georgia and adds significant biostratigraphic information to better correlate Sarmatian deposits and to better understand the palaeogeographic evolution.

The studied Sarmatian deposits are characterised by a rather diverse foraminiferal fauna (Maissuradze et al., 2004; Koiava, 2004, 2006a,b; Maissuradze, Koiava, 2006). The investigated material has been collected in 12 outcrops from Eastern Georgia: six of them are outcropping sections along rivers: Aragvi, Rusiani, Satskhenisi, Frone, Tbilisi-Gombori road, Baramaant-khevi; the other six are oil wells: Eldari N1, Taribana N39 and 40, Vashliani N1 and 10, Karas N1. Five characteristic complexes are distinguished on the basis of changes in the composition of foraminiferal assemblages. The four lower complexes are defined according to the first appearance of the species *Varidentella reussi*, *Elphidium aculeatum*, *Affinetrina voloshinova*, and *Porosonion aragviensis*, respectively. The fifth complex is defined on the basis of the dominance of *Porosonion hyalinum* (Figure).

EARLY SARMATIAN DEPOSITS

The Early Sarmatian deposits overlie the Konkian sediments and are represented by argillaceous sandstone facies (sandstones, clays, sandy clays, argillaceous sandstones). Like in the other parts of the Crimea-Caucasian region, the Early Sarmatian of Eastern Georgia is divided into two parts: lower (*Varidentella reussi* beds) and upper (*Elphidium aculeatum* beds).

The *Varidentella reussi* beds: The lower part of Early Sarmatian is characterised by two different assemblages of foraminifera. In littoral or shallow basin deposits, *Elphidium macellum* (F. et M.), *E. obtusum* (d'Orb.), *Elphidiella artifex* (Serova), *Nonion tumidulus* Pish., *Sinuloculina nitens* (Reuss), *Porosonion subgranosum* (Egger), *P. martkobi* (Bogd.), and *Varidentella reussi* (Bogd.)

The *Elphidium aculeatum* beds: the upper part of the Early Sarmatian is characterised by different foraminiferal assemblages according to the palaeoenvironment. In the littoral zone dominate mainly the species *Nonion*, *Elphidium*, and *Porosonion*, whereas miliolida such as *Varidentella reussi* (Bogd.), *Articulina problema* Bogd., and *Sinuloculina consobrina* (d'Orb.) dominate in deep-water deposits. Together with miliolida occur nonionidas such as *Nonion bogdanowiczi* Volosh. and *Porosonion subgranosum* (Egger). These species are characterised by a thin wall texture.

In the upper part of the Early Sarmatian, together with forms that are characteristic for the lower beds, the following endemic species and subspecies occur: *Elphidium aculeatum* d'Orb., *Sinuloculina consobrina sarmatica* (Gerke), *Cycloforina karreri ovata* (Serova), *C. complanata* (G. et Yss.), *Elphidium macellum converia* Vengl., and others. The appearance of new species and subspecies and the richness of samples were taken into account to place the lower/upper Early Sarmatian boundary.

MIDDLE SARMATIAN DEPOSITS

They are represented by clays and sandstones with levels of limestones, marls and conglomerates. According to foraminifera the Middle Sarmatian is divided into three parts: *Affinetrina voloshinovae* (Bogd.), *Porosonion aragviensis* (O. Djan.), and *Porosonion hyalinum* (Bogd.) beds.

The *Affinetrina voloshinovea* beds. The lower part of Middle Sarmatian is represented by deep-water deposits. Foraminifera assemblages (Taribani and Eldari outcrops) consist of *Affinetrina voloshinovae* (Bogd.), *A. guriana* (O. Djan.), *Quinqueloculina collaris* (G. et Iss.), *Sinuloculina angustioris* (Bogd.), *Cycloforina complanata* (G. et Yss.), *C. karreri ovata* (Serova), *Flintina tutkowskii* Bogd., *Articulina problema* Bogd., *Articularia articulinoidea* (Ger. et Iss.), *Sarmatiella costata* Bogd., *S. moldawiensis* Bogd., *Dogielina kaptarenko* Didk., *Meandroloculina gracilis* Bogd., *Fissurina elongata* (Pobed.), *Fisurina cubanica* (Bogd.), *Nonion bogdanowiczi* Volosh., *N. tumidulus* Pish., *Elphidium hauerinum* (d'Orb.), *Porosonion granosum* (d'Orb.), *P. subgranosum subgranosum* (Egger), and *P. subgranosum umboelata* (Gerke). The coeval outcrops along the rivers Prone and Satskhenisi are characterised by a different assemblage dominated by *Porosonion*. They are distinguished by roughly ornamented and large-sized tests. Together with *Porosonion* abundant ostracodes, fish otoliths, and remains of crayfish can be found.

The *Porosonion aragviensis* beds. The middle part of the Middle Sarmatian is characterised by the highest diversity and richness of foraminifera. The number of endemic species and subspecies, their sizes, and the degree of variability remarkably increase. In particular, species size reaches its maximum (e.g., some species of *Elphidium* display diameters of more than 1 mm). The sandy-argillaceous deposits of this level are characterised by the following assemblage: *Elphidium macellum macellum* (F. et M.), *E. macellum tumidocamerale* Bogd., *E. crispum* (Linné), *E. regina* (d'Orb.), *E. fichtellianum* d'Orb., *E. ukrainicum* Krash., *Porosonion hyalinum* (Bogd.), and *P. aragviensis* (O. Djan.). Together with foraminifera abundant large ostracodes with thick walls can be found. In Kartli, this assemblage is characteristic for outcrops along the rivers Prone, Aragvi, and Baramaantkhevi. In the area of Kakheti, synchronous deposits are represented by *Porosonion granosum* (d'Orb.), *P. subgranosum subgranosum* (Egger), *P. subgranosum umboelata* (Gerke), *P. hyalinum* (Bogd.), *P. aragviensis* (O. Djan.), *Nonion bogdanowiczi* Volosh., *Elphidium hauerinum* (d'Orb.), and *E. flexuosum* (d'Orb.). *Porosonion* and *Nonion* are distinguished by the large size of the tests, with ornamentations characteristic of the Middle Sarmatian. Very large *Articularia articulinoidea* (Ger. et Iss.), *A. sarmatica* Krerr, and *Dogielina sarmatica* Bogd. et Volosh. with thick walls are also present. This stratigraphical level is also characterised by the nonio-miliolidian-elphidiumian assemblage: *Affinetrina voloshinovae voloshinovae* (Bogd.), *A. voloshinovae eldarica* sp. nov., *A. voloshinova pecteniformis* (Bogd.), *Dogielina sarmatica* Bogd. et Volosh., *Sarmatiella prima* Bogd., *S. costata* Bogd., *S. subtilis*

(Bogd.), *S. moldawiensis* Bogd., *Sinuloculina angustioris* (Bogd.), *Articularia articulinoidea* (Ger. et Iss.), *Meandroloculina conicocameralis* Bogd., *M. schirwanensis* Bogd., *Nonion bogdanowiczii* Volosh., *Porosonion granosum* (d'Orb.), *P. subgranosum* (Egger), *Elphidium macellum* (F. et M.), and *E. fichtellianum* d'Orb. The same assemblage is present in the outcrops of Vashliani N1 and 10, and on the river Rusiani.

The *Porosonion hyalinum* beds. The upper part of the Middle Sarmatian is represented by shallow-water deposits but the composition of this assemblage differs from the lower one in species richness and diversity. In particular, only *Porosonion hyalinum* (Bogd.), *P. aragviensis* (O. Djan.), *P. subgranosum umboelata* (Gerke), *Elphidium rugosum* d'Orb., *E. macellum* (F. et M.), and *Elphidium crispum* (Linné) are present.

In conclusion, the detailed analysis of the vertical distribution of foraminifera in Sarmatian deposits of Eastern Georgia allows establishing several assemblages characterizing (a) the Lower Sarmatian beds with *Varidentella reussi* and *Elphidium aculeatum*; (b) the Middle Sarmatian beds with *Affinetrina voloshinovae*, *Porosonion aragviensis*, and *Porosonion hyalinum*.

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